

Project Number:
Project Acronym:

101081883
P2GreenN
Deliverable 6.3

Horizon Europe Programme
HORIZON-CL6-2022-ZEROPOLLUTION-01

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe Research and Innovation Programme, under Grant Agreement No°101081883.

Start date of project: 1st December 2022

Duration: 48 months

D6.3 – Project website & P2GreenN promotion package and visual identity established.

Closing the gap between fork and farm for circular nutrient flows

Deliverable details	
Work Package Title	WP6 – Communication, Exploitation, Dissemination
Task Number	T6.2 & T6.3
Deliverable Number	D6.3
Deliverable Title	Project website & P2Green promotion package and visual identity established
Revision Number	5
Responsible Organisation	C.I.P Citizens in Power
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Due Date	Friday, March 31, 2023
Delivered Date	Friday, March 31, 2023
Reviewed by	Laura Vivani
Dissemination level	PU
Please cite as	Stavrou C, Georgiou L, D6.3 Project website & P2Green promotion package and visual identity established, 2023, P2Green Consortium. Accessible at www.p2green.eu
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Project website & P2GreenN promotion package and visual identity established

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1. Introduction

This deliverable summarises the work done for the P2Green Tasks 6.2 and 6.3 which are part of work package 6. Considering the visual representation of the P2Green project, a unique image design is commenced to be the project's logo and identity. It concerns presentations, infographics, social media, and communication materials for creating the website and social media posts.

Several components in the project communication package may be used for various communication channels adjusted for the P2Green visual identity's style. The project's unique recognition value and lasting impression are the goals of this strategy.

This document provides a high-level overview of the primary P2Green materials created to assist project communication and dissemination operations.

1.1 Project Objectives

The P2Green project focuses on the transformation of linearly organised resource and nutrient systems within the agri-food supply chain, by creating a circular material flow system between urban and rural areas. One of the objectives is to restore the coupling of the water and agri-food systems using a holistic symbiotic resource management approach based on the 3R principle "Reduce, Reuse, Recover". To achieve this outcome, P2Green will develop innovative circular governance solutions for the transition from fork to farm to halt, and consequently eliminate nitrogen (N) and phosphorus (P) pollution. The newly developed solutions principles will be based on the connection between the blue urban and green rural infrastructure with a main focus on circular nutrient flows of N & P. The implementation of innovative recovery solutions for (N) & P will allow the use of human sanitary waste from urban areas with the purpose to convert it into safe bio-based fertilisers for agricultural production. This will be done by 1) demonstrating circular value chains in three pilot regions based on a north-south trajectory from the Baltic Sea region (Gotland Island) via the metropolitan area of Hamburg-Hannover to the region of Axarquia in Southern Spain, and 2) strengthening the impact by adding four follower regions in Hungary, Italy, France, and Greece.

1.2 Project Implementation

Regarding implementing the innovative circular systems, P2Green pilot regions will provide an operational environment for developing, adapting, and demonstrating the innovative systems. P2Green will support sustainable food systems by adjusting viable alternatives to reduce the use of mineral fertilisers and replace them with Green bio-based fertilisers, consequently preserving natural resources, particularly water, and soil. P2Green's sustainable circular economy models could be further adapted by policymakers, potentially replicating them across Europe.

2. Project branding

2.1 Project Visual Identity

A strong visual identity and the promotion of “brand” recognition is a key communication objectives. The P2Green visual identity comprises a professionally designed logo, colour schemes, and templates for the deliverables, presentations, newsletters, and letterhead.

2.1.1 Logo

Considering P2Green's visual identity, the initial action was creating a visible and original identity, the project's official logo, and colour scheme. The selection of the official logo was based on the agreement between all the partners. Therefore, the logo is to be used in official documents, on the project's website, newsletters, flyers and brochures. **Figure 1** presents P2Green's official logo.

Figure 1: The official logo of the project to be used in all contexts

The arrows in P2Green's logo symbolise the circular economy/system that the consortium aims to establish, while the gaps between the arrows symbolise the gaps that the P2Green project aims to close. The three arrows have different meanings: a) the three pilot regions of P2Green, b) the 3R principle that underpins all activities within P2Green (i.e., Reduce, Reuse, Recover) and c) the envisioned circular

nutrient flows (blue for nutrient collection in urban settlements, dark green for the use of processed nutrients in agriculture for food production, and light green for the return of nutrients to settlements as food).

2.1.2 Colour scheme

P2Green's color scheme is inspired by the EU's call for zero pollution and the interconnection between land and water. The designers have chosen colors that remind the viewer of water and the land-use sector, as the P2Green project focuses on the connection between blue urban infrastructure and green rural infrastructure. The grain symbolizes agriculture, which is a central aspect of our project. P2Green's goal is to bridge the gap between fork and farm to foster zero pollution and circular (nutrient) systems.

2.1.3 Project acronym

The project acronym, P2Green, features capital P and capital N, which refer to phosphorus and nitrogen, respectively. P2Green's goal is to reduce N and P pollution in the environment and instead use these nutrients for growing food sustainably. The title also intends to encourage associations to Pee that will fertilise the soil as a green fertiliser for sustainable agriculture and food production. Also, the title refers to "Pee" (human excreta) being used to produce new "Green", which means agriculture in this context ("pee to green"). Furthermore, capital G refers to governance and a green transition, which are essential elements of the EU call and the project.

2.1.4 Visual Identity Guidelines

The logo should always be placed in a prominent position so that it appears clearly. It should appear on all brochure covers and advertisements, in both print and electronic versions. Around the logo, there should always be enough space to ensure a powerful and clear visual image. The amount of clear space is in direct proportion to the size of the P2Green logo and must not be altered.

The size of the logo will vary from one application to another. The minimum size is indicated by the width of the logo. For all printed material, the minimum width of the logo is 20 mm and 70 pixels for digital use.

To keep consistency and to have inclusive and accessible materials, the project consortium used the following fonts:

In all the deliverables:

- First level heading (use style: Arial, 16 pt, bold, font color: RGB(128,141,144))
- Body text: Arial, 12 pt
- Second level heading (use style: Arial, 13 pt, bold, font color: Automatic)
- Body text: Arial, 12 pt
- Third level heading (use style: Arial, 12 pt, bold, italic, font color: Automatic)
- Body text: Arial, 12 pt

In all the PowerPoint presentations:

- Title (use style: Calibri Light, 44 pt, bold)
- Subtitle (use style: Nunito Sans Bold, 28 pt, bold)
- Text (use style: Nunito Sans Bold, 28 pt)

In the flyer:

- Title (use style: Nunito Sans Black, 23.5 pt, font color: #487307)
- Subtitle (use style: Nunito Sans Bold, 14.1 pt, font color: #487307)
- Text (use style: Nunito Sans Bold, 7.9 pt, font color: #141414)

For bullet list, use:

- Bullet 1

For number list, use:

1. Number 1

For figures and tables:

Figure 1: Example of figure

Heading 1	Heading 2	

Table 1 Example of table

2.2 P2Green Website

2.2.1 Website Structure

P2Green's website includes all the relevant project information regarding the objectives, target groups, information of the participating partners, events timeline, and latest activities news. The homepage section provides the relevant information for the project's objective and the pilot and follower regions. The About the Project page presents the timeframe, specific goals and measurable outcomes. Regarding the project's work packages, a Work Package section shows all the activities with relevant information for each. For further engagement with people and

dissemination, a Contact Us page section is available that allows the completion of a filling form and all the necessary contact details.

In addition, the website includes all the project's social platform links (Facebook, Twitter, Instagram, and LinkedIn). **The website's URL is <https://p2green.eu/>.**

2.2.2 Website architecture and sections

The website architecture is based on different sections and sub-sections as follows:

- **Home**

The home section briefly explains the project's overall objective and provides information regarding the consortium, the work packages, and P2Green's pilot and follower regions. **Figure 2** illustrates P2Green's website homepage.

- **About the project**

This section gives insight into the rationale for the innovation solutions P2Green aims to establish. It presents the P2Green's specific objectives and measurable outcomes for each timeframe. **Figure 3** illustrates P2Green's about the project.

- **Work Packages**

The key elements which the P2Green project aims to address for each work package are described in this section. **Figure 4** illustrates P2Green's work packages.

- **Events**

A thorough overview of the interdisciplinary team supporting P2Green and how their combined knowledge and experience support and contribute to the project's intended results. **Figure 5** illustrates P2Green's events page.

- **Contact Us**

- Contact details
- Contact form

Figure 6 illustrates P2Green's contact us page.

- **News**

It will serve as the project's communication engine, delivering news, events, and newsletter. **Figure 7** illustrates P2Green's news page.

Figure 2: P2Green's website homepage

Figure 3: P2Green's about the project

Figure 4: P2Green's work packages

Figure 5: P2Green's events page

Figure 6: P2GreenN's contact us

Figure 7: P2GreenN's News page

2.3 Project's Social Media Platforms

Social networks are crucial for generating interest in the P2GreenN Project and enabling engagement and participation from the public. The social networks will address different target audiences and engagement activities concerning the communication and dissemination strategy and are well explained in deliverable 6.1.

Social Media Platform	Profile Name	Link
Facebook	@p2greenHorizonEU	https://www.facebook.com/p2greenHorizonEU
Twitter	@P2green_Horizon	https://twitter.com/P2green_Horizon
Instagram	@p2green	https://instagram.com/p2green
LinkedIn	@P2Green	https://www.linkedin.com/company/p2green/
Youtube	@p2green	https://www.youtube.com/@p2green

Table 1: P2GreenN social media platforms

2.3.1 Facebook Page

The Facebook page of the project, at the time of writing, reached 137 followers and 130 likes. The estimated reach by the end of the project is 500 likes, posts, and followers.

Figure 8: P2GreenN's Facebook page

2.3.2 Twitter Page

The Twitter page of the project, at the time of writing, reached 69 followers. The estimated reach by the end of the project is 800 tweets, retweets, and followers.

Figure 9: P2Green's Twitter page

2.3.3 Instagram Page

The Instagram page of the project, at the time of writing, reached 117 followers. The estimated reach by the end of the project is 500 likes, posts, and followers.

Figure 10: P2GreenN's Instagram page

2.3.4 LinkedIn Page

The LinkedIn page of the project at the time of writing, reached 181 followers. The target is to reach 1000 likes, group members, or posts by the end of the project.

Figure 11: P2GreenN's Twitter page

2.3.5 Youtube Page

The Youtube page of the P2GreenN project at the time of writing this deliverable, reached 8 subscribers and one video was published. The target is to reach 500 viewers in total.

Figure 12: P2GreenN's Youtube page

2.4 P2Green Template

A series of templates was designed for partners to ensure brand consistency, recognition and visibility of P2Green and its key results. The purpose of each template and dissemination material, is explained in Table 4 of the D6.1

2.4.1 Deliverable template

A word template was designed for the project's deliverables. It is available for download on the P2Green MS teams workplace:

Figure 13: P2Green deliverable template

PowerPoint template

A PowerPoint presentation template was designed to be used by all partners for internal meetings, and when presenting the project at external events (conferences,

workshops, meetings with stakeholders, etc.). It is available for download on the P2Green MS Teams workplace:

Figure 14: PowerPoint presentation template

2.4.2 EU emblem

According to the European Commission Horizon Europe rules, all materials, including scientific papers and publications produced by the project, must contain the mandatory EU emblem with the following funding acknowledgment and required disclaimer with the sentences below. Moreover, it is important to note that “when displayed together with another logo, the EU emblem must have appropriate prominence”:

Figure 15: EU emblem

In all the materials that disseminate the project's results (publications), the acknowledgement must also include a disclaimer excluding the European Commission's responsibility.

Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or [name of the granting authority]. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

2.4.3 Partner's logos

To facilitate the use of partners' logos and avoid incorrect practices when using multiple logos, a banner was designed to be used in relevant documentation (paper or electronic), and promotional materials produced by the project. It is available for download in PNG format on the P2Green MS Teams workplace:

Figure 16: P2Green partners' logo banner 1

Figure 17: P2Green partners' logos banner 2

Annexe I

Project Flyer

P2Green **TURNING HUMAN SANITARY WASTE INTO FERTILIZER**

Funded by the European Union

P2Green's overall objective is to foster a paradigm shift, from a linearly organised resource and nutrient system within the agri-food supply chain, towards a circular material flow system between urban and rural areas thereby restoring the coupling of the water-agri-food system using a holistic symbiotic resource management approach following the 3R principle "Reduce, Reuse, Recover".

Work Packages

- 01 Blueprinting the regional clusters**
Test and demonstrate the N&P circular systems in the 3 pilot regions.
- 02 Monitoring & assessing the benefits**
Assess and validate the sustainability and impacts of the circular N & P systems demonstrated in the 3 pilot regions.
- 03 Supporting the transition**
Shaping the transition to innovative circular systems for the conversion of human sanitary waste into safe bio-based N & P fertilisers.
- 04 Building the governance framework**
Develop the P2Green cross-cutting governance framework.
- 05 Upscaling the impact**
Implement a series of actions that will allow P2Green's innovative and transformative circular solutions to be adopted and scaled within follower regions and across the EU.
- 06 Communication, Exploitation, Dissemination**
Raise awareness and promote P2Green's innovative governance solutions across Europe.
- 07 Project Management**
Ensure efficient and timely implementation of the project.

3 PILOT REGIONS **32** ORGANIZATIONS
4 FOLLOWER REGIONS **13** COUNTRIES

www.p2green.eu

FOLLOW US! [p2greenHorizonEU](#) [p2green](#)

Figure 18: P2Green's project flyer

Project Brochure

Work Packages

- 01** **Blueprinting the regional clusters**
Test and demonstrate the N&P circular systems in the 3 pilot regions.
- 02** **Monitoring & assessing the benefits**
Assess and validate the sustainability and impacts of the circular N & P systems demonstrated in the 3 pilot regions.
- 03** **Supporting the transition**
Shaping the transition to innovative circular systems for the conversion of human sanitary waste into safe bio-based N & P fertilisers.
- 04** **Building the governance framework**
Develop the P2GreenN cross-cutting governance framework.
- 05** **Upscaling the impact**
Implement a series of actions that will allow P2GreenN's innovative and transformative circular solutions to be adopted and scaled within follower regions and across the EU.
- 06** **Communication, Exploitation, Dissemination**
Raise awareness and promote P2GreenN's innovative governance solutions across Europe.
- 07** **Project Management**
Ensure efficient and timely implementation of the project.

Funded by the European Union

New standards for resource efficiency

3 PILOT REGIONS	32 ORGANIZATIONS
4 FOLLOWER REGIONS	13 COUNTRIES

www.p2green.eu

FOLLOW US: p2green

TURNING HUMAN SANITARY WASTE INTO FERTILIZER

What is behind the idea?

Agriculturally grown food is produced with the addition of energy-intensive fertilizers, the consumer consumes it and this is where the chain ends. But it makes more sense to develop a cycle that eliminates fertilizers from costly production and negative effects on our environment, as well as the waste of nutrient-rich wastewater from cities.

What is the solution?

The circle can be closed by using human sanitary waste and converting it into bio-based fertilizers, utilizing important nutrients that are produced in large quantities every day anyway. The key lies in nutrient recovery.

About the project

December 1, 2022 was the starting date for our four-year EU project P2GreenN, which will develop, test and adapt the use of human sanitary waste to produce safe, bio-based fertilizers for agriculture. Our consortium of 32 European partners scored well with the Horizon Europe program and we have been awarded the contract to implement this unprecedented project.

Vast amounts of wastewater with a high nutrient content disappear daily into the sewers of large cities. On the other hand, agriculture, using conventional fertilizers, struggles to produce good yields in the fields to feed the growing world population. What some have too much of, others have too little of. There must be a solution to this.

Vision

Develop and demonstrate viable and sustainable approaches to nutrient recovery from sanitary waste.

Mission

Develop, test and adapt the use of human sanitary waste to produce safe, bio-based fertilizers for agriculture.

Funded by the European Union

Figure 19: P2GreenN's project brochure

Project Rollup

The graphic features a central circular logo with a green recycling symbol and a leaf, with the text 'P2GreenN' in the center. Above the logo is the European Union flag and the text 'Funded by the European Union'. Below the logo, the text 'P2GreenN' is written in large green letters. Underneath, a paragraph describes the project: 'Develop, test and adapt the use of human sanitary waste to produce safe, bio-based fertilizers for agriculture.' To the left of this paragraph are three statistics: '32 ORGANIZATIONS', '13 COUNTRIES', and '3 PILOT REGIONS'. To the right are two more statistics: '4 FOLLOWER REGIONS' and 'New standards for resource efficiency' with a leaf icon. At the bottom, the website 'www.p2green.eu' is displayed, followed by social media icons for Facebook, Instagram, and LinkedIn with the handles 'p2greenHorizonEU' and 'p2green'.

Funded by the European Union

P2GreenN

Develop, test and adapt the use of human sanitary waste to produce safe, bio-based fertilizers for agriculture.

32 ORGANIZATIONS

13 COUNTRIES

3 PILOT REGIONS

4 FOLLOWER REGIONS

New standards for resource efficiency

www.p2green.eu

FOLLOW US! p2greenHorizonEU p2green

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European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement No° 101081883

Figure 20: P2GreenN's project rollup

Letterhead Template

Figure 21: P2GreenN's letterhead template

Contact

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www.instagram.com/p2green/

www.twitter.com/P2green_Horizon

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